

SCALE MODEL SPACE SHUTTLE EMI TEST: HF-VHF ELECTROMAGNETIC FIELD STRENGTH MEASUREMENTS

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ABSTRACT

This paper introduces the Waves in Space Plasmas (WISP) project and documents the results of an EMI test with the Dipole Antenna Subsystem (DASS) portion of the project. The National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) is concerned that the electromagnetic fields radiated by the dipole antenna may be large enough to interfere with, or prevent, the operation of other mission equipment on the Shuttle. This test uses a one-tenth scale model of the Orbiter, DASS and payloads to measure the electromagnetic field levels in the Orbiter cargo bay. These field strength values are compared to values obtained from computer models.

INTRODUCTION

The WISP experiment is a cooperative effort between the United States and Canada to study the physics of waves in space plasmas. WISP will carry out experiments in the earth's ionosphere on the generation, propagation and detection of waves in a plasma environment. The Orbiter-based transmitter for WISP will use a dipole antenna of variable length, up to 50 meters tip-to-tip, and will operate at power levels between 1 milliwatt and 500 watts. The receivers for the WISP experiment will be located on both the Shuttle Orbiter and on a free-flying satellite. The on-orbit configuration for the WISP experiment is shown in Figure 1.

The WISP experiment will operate between 0.1 and 30 MHz, which corresponds to wavelengths between 10 meters and 3 kilometers. Thus, at any frequency used during the WISP experiment, the Orbiter payloads will be in the near field of the DASS antenna, which is a source of EMI. Because the WISP experiment configuration on the Orbiter is physically complex and difficult to model mathematically, tests were run to predict the field strength levels radiated by the DASS antenna. The WISP EMI test used a 1/10 scale model of the Orbiter, its payloads and the dipole antenna. The entire model was constructed in two laterally symmetrical halves. The magnitude of the electromagnetic fields was recorded at several points in the Orbiter cargo bay using a Narda Model 8716 meter

and Narda Models 8760, 8761, 8731 and 8752 broadband isotropic electric and magnetic field probes. Since the Orbiter model is one tenth the size of the actual Orbiter, the EMI test frequencies were scaled to ten times the WISP operating frequencies, and the recorded electric and magnetic field strength values were scaled to one tenth their measured values. All results presented here are scaled to 250 watts radiated by the WISP antenna. All coordinates are relative to the Orbiter coordinate system, where the origin is located 5.1 meters ahead of the nose on the x axis, on the centerline of the cargo bay on the y axis and 10.2 meters below the centerline of the cargo bay on the z axis.

Figure 1. WISP Experiment On-Orbit Configuration

OUTDOOR EMI TEST

The WISP EMI test measured the electric and magnetic field intensities at both an outdoor site and in an anechoic chamber. For the outdoor portion of the WISP EMI test, a single half of the Orbiter model was placed over a metallic ground plane with the cargo bay floor perpendicular to the earth's surface. A mirror image of the half shuttle was formed below the earth because of the presence of the ground plane. Figure 2 shows the configuration for the outdoor portion of the EMI test.

Figure 2. Outdoor EMI Test Configuration

The ground plane, which is shown in Figure 3, consisted of a 170 cm by 375 cm rectangular aluminum sheet, electrically connected to a circular copper mesh, 10 meters in diameter, which was, in turn, connected to the earth with grounding rods. A total of 120 copper radials, each 120 meters in length, were connected every three degrees at the edge of the copper mesh in order to insure that the ground plane was electrically large enough (greater than 0.4 wavelengths at the lowest test frequency).

Figure 3. EMI Test Ground Plane

Because of the complexities involved in the outdoor portion of the WISP EMI test, a graduated test approach was used to help build confidence that the field strength measurements taken during the outdoor test would be accurate. The graduated test approach began by comparing measured field strength values to computed values for a vertical monopole over a perfectly conducting ground plane. Since the fields from the monopole are well-characterized mathematically, the measured fields and the calculated fields can be easily compared. Once the measured field values from the monopole were

validated by the numerical models, the measured and computed field strengths were compared for the WISP antenna located near an empty rectangular box of the same dimensions as the Orbiter cargo bay. Once the fields from this configuration compared favorably with the computed values, the fields were measured for the tenth-scale model of the WISP experiment.

Figure 4 shows the electric field intensity at $X=18.31\text{m}$, $Y=0.76\text{m}$ and $Z=10.3\text{m}$ in the Orbiter cargo bay for tenth-scale antenna lengths of 0.5, 1.5 and 5 meters, which corresponds to full scale lengths of 5, 15 and 50 meters. As mentioned above, the power radiated by each antenna is scaled to 250 watts. Notice that the field from the short (0.5 meter) antenna is maximum at 300 MHz, which is the resonant, or half-wavelength, frequency for a 0.5 meter dipole in free space. The field from the long (5 meter) antenna is also maximum near its resonant frequency of 30 MHz. The medium (1.5 meter) antenna field has a peak at its resonant frequency, 100 MHz, but the fields from the medium antenna are maximum at 300 MHz.

Figure 4. Electric Field for 0.5, 1.5 and 5m Antennas

ANECHOIC CHAMBER TEST

Since computer memory limitations precluded modeling the WISP experiment configuration numerically, the field strengths measured with the WISP experiment configuration in the outdoor test were validated by a similar indoor test. For this portion of the WISP EMI test, the two halves of the Orbiter model and its payloads were joined together and placed in the anechoic chamber facility at Marshall Space Flight Center (MSFC), as shown in Figure 5. The electric and magnetic field intensities were measured at the same points in the cargo bay as in the outdoor test. Since the MSFC anechoic chamber is not calibrated below 100 MHz, the anechoic chamber portion of the test was performed only between 100 MHz and 300 MHz, and was used to show that the image concept used during the outdoor portion of the test is valid.

Figure 5. Anechoic Chamber EMI Test Configuration

Figure 6 shows the electric and magnetic field intensities from the short antenna at 300 MHz for $Z = 10.3$ meters, which is 1.24 meters beneath the plane of the antenna. The remaining test points, not shown in this figure, lie in the $Z = 8.71$ meter plane. Note that even though the field strengths are strongest near the antenna, a local maximum exists approximately one wavelength (1m) away from the antenna, at point 22.

Although the electric and magnetic fields were measured on only one side of the cargo bay, tests showed that the field strengths were laterally symmetrical. As expected, the field intensities decreased with increasing distance from the antenna.

Figure 6. Fields from Short Antenna at 300 MHz

COMPUTER MODELING

As mentioned in the previous section, the WISP experiment on-orbit configuration is difficult to accurately model mathematically. However, as a second method for verifying the results of the outdoor EMI test, the fields from the wire antenna/empty rectangular box configuration were calculated using the Numerical Electromagnetics Code (NEC) [1] [2], and compared to the fields measured during the graduated test approach. NEC uses the electric field integral equation (EFIE) and the magnetic field integral equation (MFIE) to solve for the currents induced on a given structure. The code then uses the method of moments (MOM) to find the electric and magnetic fields from these induced currents. Table 1

compares electric field strengths from the rectangular box/wire antenna model of the cargo bay measured during the outdoor EMI test with the same values calculated by NEC.

Antenna	X,Y,Z (meters)	Outdoor	NEC	Ratio
Short	17.83, 1.5, 10.3	34.6 V/m	30.1 V/m	1.2:1
Short	23.93, 1.5, 10.3	64.3 V/m	53.5 V/m	1.2:1
Short	26.97, 1.5, 10.3	69.5 V/m	44.6 V/m	1.6:1
Long	20.88, 1.5, 10.3	3.5 V/m	4.9 V/m	1.4:1
Long	23.93, 1.5, 10.3	5.1 V/m	4.6 V/m	1.1:1
Long	26.97, 0.75, 8.7	3.6 V/m	5.0 V/m	1.4:1

Table 1. Comparison of Electric Field Strengths Between Outdoor EMI Test and NEC

CONCLUSIONS

The results from the outdoor EMI test, which used one half of the Orbiter model, compare closely with the results of the anechoic chamber EMI test, which used the two halves of the model joined together. These results seem to validate the theory that, for the outdoor EMI test, an image of the half Orbiter model is indeed formed beneath the model itself because of the presence of the ground plane. To illustrate the close agreement between the anechoic chamber and outdoor test results, Figure 7 compares the measured field strengths from the anechoic chamber and outdoor tests for a specific test case, the long antenna at 300 MHz located at X=32.31m, Y=1.52m and Z=10.3m. Notice that, at this location, the electric and magnetic field strengths from the anechoic chamber test are within a factor of two of the corresponding values from the outdoor test.

Figure 7. Anechoic Chamber/Outdoor EMI Test Field Strength Comparison

Finally, Table 1 indicates that the fields calculated by NEC also agree closely with the fields measured from the outdoor EMI test. For the test cases shown, the results from NEC and the outdoor test agree to within a factor of 2.

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REFERENCES

- [1] J. Fryer and F. Ingels, "Investigation of WISP Near Fields Data," Final Report of NASA Grant NAG8-104, Volume 3, pp. 191-221, December 1992.

- [2] G. J. Burke and A. J. Poggio, "Numerical Electromagnetics Code (NEC) - Method of Moments, Part I," Document No. UCID-18834, an informal report by Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory for the U.S. Dept. of Energy under Contract W-7405-Eng-48, January 1981.